

Studies on the Role of Metal Ions in Formation of Clay-Humus Complex

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The role of metal cations in the formation of clay-humus complex has been studied. It has been found that the interaction between clay and humus is dependent on the degrees of saturation of the metal ions and also on the nature of the cations present in the clay. The binding is more strong in presence of Fe and less in presence of Ca. Al has an intermediate effect.

THE actual nature of linkage between humus substances and clay minerals remains obscure. According to Aleksandrova¹ stable clay humus complexes are formed in the soil with the help of sesquioxides, which make specific bridges between humus substances and crystalline lattice of clay minerals. Sen² suggests that during the interaction of clay with humic acids two types of linkage take place : (a) unstable-humic acid is arranged on the external surface of the clay and this can be easily extracted by alkali ; (b) stable type of linkage is formed by the interaction of clay, humic acid and the exchangeable cations occurring in the lattice of the clay minerals. In the present communication the role of metal ions at different degrees of saturation in the formation of clay-humus complex has been studied.

Experimental

Humus was extracted from Assam soil by a mixture of a solution of 0.1N NaOH and 0.1M $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ (pH 13). It was fractionated to humic and fulvic acids and subsequently purified. The detail description of the method of fractionation and purification was given earlier³.

H-clay was obtained from Behar bentonite by the usual procedures. The b.e.c. was determined by titrating with baryta (using phenolphthalin as indicator) in presence of 1N BaCl_2 solution and was found to be 83 me/100 g.

The Ca-clays at different degrees of calcium saturation were prepared by adding calcium hydroxide in equivalent amounts to the hydrogen clay. Fe- and Al-clays were prepared by leaching the H-clay with equivalent amount of the solutions of FeCl_3 and AlCl_3 respectively. The leached clays were washed free from electrolytes.

The different clays were then treated with Na-humate solution (pH 8). The mixture was kept for one month for interaction with occasional shaking and then centrifuged. The unadsorbed Na-humate in the centrifugate was estimated colorimetrically. For this purpose, a standard curve was first of all made by plotting

optical densities at 470 nm against known concentrations of Na-humate in the region where linearity was followed. The method was described in detail by Banerjee⁴ and Roy *et al.*⁵. The residue after centrifuging the Na-humate was treated separately with 0.5N Na_2CO_3 solution and shaken and kept for 48 hr. The material was again centrifuged and the amount of Na-humate released was estimated colorimetrically.

In a separate set of experiments, the different clays (100% saturation with the metal ions) were treated with concentrated solution of Na-humate and the mixture was kept for one month. The unadsorbed Na-humate was removed. The clay-humus mixture was treated separately with 0.5N Na_2CO_3 solution and 0.1M $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ solution. The humus extracted was treated with concentrated HCl to pH 2-3 and the humic acid precipitated was dialysed. The dialysed material was subjected to electrometric studies.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the results of the sorption and desorption of Na-humate on and from different clays of different degrees of saturation with metal ions. The results obtained show that a portion of the adsorbed Na-humate is not extractable by alkali treatment. The strong binding between clays and Na-humate is probably of a chemical nature and with the increase of the metallic ion saturation, the interaction is not only more extensive but the intensity of interaction increases appreciably.

The interaction is also dependent on the nature of the cation present in the clay. The binding is more strong in presence of iron and less in presence of Ca. Al has an intermediate effect. At the time of extraction of humus from these different clays by 0.5 N Na_2CO_3 solution appreciable amount of the humus is retained in the system as clay-humus complex and the metal ions probably form "specific bridges" between humus substances and clays¹.

TABLE 1—SORPTION AND DESORPTION OF Na-HUMATES ON AND FROM DIFFERENT CLAYS

Wt. of clays taken- 0.3036 g
Wt. of Na-humate taken- 0.0076 g

Percentage saturation	Percent of Na-humate added	Percent unadsorbed	Percent adsorbed	Percent released after one extraction with 0.5N Na ₂ CO ₃ soln	Percent fixed
Ca-clay					
0	2.5	0.925	1.575	0.583	0.972
25	2.5	0.780	1.720	0.564	1.156
50	2.5	0.645	1.855	0.579	1.276
75	2.5	0.455	2.045	0.569	1.476
100	2.5	0.328	2.172	0.519	1.653
Al-clay					
0	2.5	0.925	1.575	0.583	0.972
25	2.5	0.735	1.765	0.452	1.313
50	2.5	0.545	1.955	0.434	1.521
75	2.5	0.328	2.172	0.432	1.740
100	2.5	0.205	2.295	0.353	1.942
Fe-clay					
0	2.5	0.925	1.575	0.583	0.972
25	2.5	0.555	1.945	0.560	1.385
50	2.5	0.410	2.090	0.472	1.618
75	2.5	0.270	2.230	0.363	1.867
100	2.5	0.153	2.347	0.279	2.068

TABLE 2—TOTAL ACIDITIES OF THE ACIDS EXTRACTED BY THE TWO REAGENTS

Exchange capacity of the original acid = 640 me/100 g

Humic acids from	Extracted by	
	Na ₂ CO ₃ solution	Na ₄ P ₂ O ₇
Ca-clay-humus complex	610	622
Al-clay-humus complex	510	613
Fe-clay-humus complex	490	595

The exchange capacities of the humic acid (determined by pH titration using NaOH as a titrant) extracted separately by Na₂CO₃ and Na₄P₂O₇ solutions from the different clay-humus complexes are given in Table 2. The original acid has the exchange capacity of 640 me/100 g³. But the exchange capacity of this acid extracted by Na₂CO₃ solution from the complexes after complex formation with Ca-Al- and Fe-clays decreases, the maximum decrease being noted when Fe is present in the system and minimum in the case of Ca. But when Na₄P₂O₇ is used as an extractant the decrease is not so pronounced. Soil humus holds certain metallic cations very firmly. It holds trivalent metallic cations much more firmly than alkali and alkaline earth metal cations⁴. Thus leaching a soil with NaCl or Na₂CO₃ solution may not remove all these cations. But pyrophosphate can easily form chelate compounds with metal ions and leaching a soil with Na-pyrophosphate solution will remove much larger proportion of di- and trivalent cations and the Na-humate thus produced will disperse relatively easily. The humic acid extracted by Na₂CO₃ solution from different clays contain appreciable quantities of the metal ions through a

specific method of bonding as chelation and the chelation appears to be through phenolic hydroxyl and carboxyl groups^{2,5,6} and due to the blocking of some of these groups there is a decrease of the total acidity of the humic acids (The acidity of humic acid depends mainly on the presence of carboxyl and phenolic hydroxyl groups) extracted by Na₂CO₃ solution from the different clay-humus complexes. But the humic acid extracted by the Na-pyrophosphate solution contains lesser amount of the metal ions as it easily forms chelate compounds with metallic cations and consequently the acidity is higher. The results are in agreement with the findings of Martin and Reeve⁷ who showed that upto pH 7 Al containing humic acid required 380 me/100 g of NaOH but for low aluminium acid required 620 me/100 g.

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